

11 On Discrete Euclidean Space

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25 February 2021

The paper is the eleventh post of the blog “Discrete Euclidean Space” at <https://www.conceptualframeworks.org>. The post is about the conceptual limitations of Einstein’s theory of Special and General relativity.

Space and time

The description of the properties of the structure of discrete space in the previous posts is not in line with the theory of Special (1905) and General relativity (1915). This cannot be a surprise because at the time that both parts of the theory were published the first reductionistic concepts of the constituents of the microcosm were just created (e.g. the Rutherford-Bohr model of the atom).

The ideas of theoretical physicists about the nature of space and time were very limited at the start of the 20th century. This in contrast with the thoughts of the Greek philosopher [Parmenides](#) (\approx 500 B.C.).^[1] He reasoned that observable reality – actually phenomenological physics – don’t exist by itself. That’s why he concluded that observable reality is created by an underlying structure that exist everywhere in the universe. Parmenides stated that “true” vacuum cannot exist in our universe.

In classic physics fields were proposed to represent some kind of “spatial extensions” of observable phenomena, like the attracting gravitational force as described by Isaac Newton.^[2] Although the “instantaneous attraction” puzzled the physicists in the 18th and 19th century. It resulted in the idea that empty space was filled with an aether, a medium of ultra thin corpuscles.

Seen with the eyes of a 19th century physicist Einstein’s idea that gravity was the reaction of space on the existence of local concentrations of mass ($E = m c^2$) was revolutionary. But the idea implies also that *every* local amount of energy causes a reaction of space. Even the mutual relations between the local amounts of energy, the electromagnetic interactions.

Figure 1 shows Einstein’s “gedanken” experiment with the rocket in space. The accelerating velocity is responsible for

the “weight” of the box on the floor of the space rocket. If there are 3 small holes in the hull of the rocket we can apply 3 different streams of photons (yellow), electrons (blue) and protons (green) trough the holes. Now what will we conclude?

We will conclude that the velocity of the stream of photons, electrons and protons are related to their individually energy content in relation to the velocity of the space rocket. We will not propose that the individual trajectories of the 3 streams inside the rocket are caused by the force of gravitation because of the proposed equivalence between gravity and acceleration.

figure 1

In 1900 Max Planck published his findings over the black body radiation and proposed the quantization of the energy of electromagnetic radiation (the quantum of energy). However, the fixed amount of energy is the fixed amount of observable change. To observe a change there must be a change of position and the change of position must have a velocity. In other words, a quantum represents:

$$d = v t \quad [d = \text{distance}; v = \text{velocity}; t = \text{duration}]$$

The static interpretation of the quantum is determined by the distance (d) between the start and the end of the fixed

change of position. The dynamical interpretation of the quantum is determined by the velocity and the duration of the fixed change of position.

Therefore I can write for one linear quantum:

$$h = v t \quad [h = \text{Planck's constant}]$$

The fixed amount of change (h) and the velocity (v) are both constants (Planck's constant and the speed of light). The quantum is the smallest fixed amount of linear change and the speed of light is the constant linear velocity of the smallest fixed amount of change. Therefore we have to conclude that the smallest amount of duration – time – is a universal constant too (see 03).

It is quite disappointing but we have to conclude that one of Einstein's main concepts in his theory of Special relativity – the existence of relative time – isn't correct.

Spacetime – Einstein's main concept in his theory of General relativity – cannot exist without the concept of relative time. In other words, if spacetime is correct, Planck's constant (h) isn't a constant at all. Unfortunately the observed variance of relative time in experiments is too much to propose that Planck's constant is the result of inaccurate measurements so it is impossible to conclude that Planck's constant represent a variable quantity within the conceptual framework of phenomenological physics..

In other words, it isn't overdone to state that at the present the basic concepts of Einstein's theory of Relativity are outdated. Unfortunately, Special and General relativity are in line with the experiments and observations...

References:

1. Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy. “*The Continuum and the Infinitesimal in the Ancient Period*” (chapter 2).
<https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/continuity>
2. Isaac Newton(1787), “*Philosophiæ Naturalis Principia Mathematica*”.
Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy.
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Velocity related change

The concept that space itself is discrete means that all the quanta transfer in the universe is conserved and synchronized because of the invariance of the volume of space itself. An invariance that is determined by the invariance of the volume of the units of the structure of discrete space.

Linear quanta have a constant velocity, the speed of light. A linear quantum is a fixed amount of topological deformation that is transferred from one unit to an adjacent unit of discrete space. If a local concentration of energy – e.g. a rest mass carrying particle – is accelerated the quanta transfer of the units of discrete space “within the boundary of the particle” is forced into the direction of the motion of the particle.

If the particle has a low velocity nearly all the quanta transfer within its boundary is nearly a closed loop (see figure 2). But if the particle has nearly the speed of light every involved unit of discrete space “within the boundary of the particle” transfers its topological deformation in the direction of the motion of the particle. As a result the internal loop of quanta transfer of the particle has decreased. Now the observer of the particle will conclude that time is relative because the external changes of the particle (or a clock) have slowed down.

figure 2

In other words, the mechanism^[3] that is responsible for the decrease of changes of objects if these objects are accelerated, is real. Therefore the problem is not the mechanism itself – experimental verified during more than a century (see reference) – but Albert Einstein proposal in his theory of Special relativity that time itself is relative. Time itself at the fundamental level of reality isn't variable, it is a constant. Perfect in line with the constant speed of light and the fixed amount of energy, Planck's constant. Therefore, relativistic quantum theories don't represent reality, these theories are founded on contradictions.

References:

3. Wilson, J.N., Thisse, D., Lebois, M. *et al.*
"Angular momentum generation in nuclear fission."
Nature 590, 566–570 (2021).
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-03304-w>

“Curved” space

Einstein’s concept of the curvature of space itself has no determined causation. Figure 1 shows the inducement of his concept: the proposed curved trajectory of a stream of quanta because an accelerating space rocket will cause internal objects to be pushed to the floor. Just like the force of gravity.

But the cause behind the “push to the floor” is described in above. It is the constant linear velocity of every quantum in the universe. The space rocket accelerates while the object inside the rocket is forced to accelerate too because it is pushed in that direction by the floor. Actually, the involved units of discrete space that represent the object at that moment have to change the variable relation between the linear motion and the internal loops of the quanta. In other words, Einstein’s idea that gravitation and acceleration are equivalent isn’t correct because the acceleration of the space rocket is determined by the local conditions of the electromagnetic field and not by the force of gravitation.

figure 3

The spatial influence of the force of Newtonian gravity – scalar vectors that emerge at the moment matter is created – can be interpreted as some kind of a geometrical curvature of points in space where the vectors have the same magnitude (figure 3, concentric circles). But vectors act instantaneous so it is impossible to state that Einstein’s curved space is equal to Newtonian gravity. The influence of Einstein’s force of gravitation is determined by the speed of light (quanta transfer in vacuum space).

Because Albert Einstein was convinced that his concept of curved spacetime described Newtonian gravity he implemented the gravitational constant in the equations of the theory of General relativity. But the electromagnetic field at the macroscopic level is a push force, creating local concentrations of energy. Like the vector field of Newtonian gravity is a push force too, concentrating matter in vacuum space. The only difference is the velocity of the influence. Einstein’s “curved spacetime” is limited by the speed of light and Newtonian gravity acts instantaneous (09; 10).

That is why observations and measurements confirm the model of General relativity. Unfortunately it also shows that the infallible scientific method isn’t always a guarantee for reliable science.